

String-Scale Gravitation and Photon Momentum

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I read recently that $\mathbb{R}^{1,3|4}$ is probably the most well-studied superspace. It makes sense; it is, after all, homeomorphic to the superspace of the classical Minkowski lightcone:

$$\mathbb{R}^{1,3|4} \simeq \mathbb{L}_{\mp}^{1,3} \tag{0.1}$$

The bosonic graviton lives in $\mathbb{L}_{+}^{1,3}$ alongside the photon; meanwhile its fermionic superpartner, the gravitino, lives in $\mathbb{L}_{-}^{1,3}$. For a lightcone, these strata are easily envisionable; we simply replace its future and past trajectories with bosonic and fermionic sectors, respectively.

It turns out, we can actually get away with doing a lot with potential theory on the lightcone without actually invoking topology much. In fact, the only topological ingredient we need is essentially differential, and that is *boundary conditions*.

The choice of appropriate boundary conditions (i.e., von Neumann vs. Dirichlet, etc.) comes down to what you want your Hilbert space to embed. I conjecture that every deformation of a lightcone's boundary conditions amounts to a unique choice of a Frobenius algebraic sequence, or \mathcal{FAS} . For the recap on these, I kindly refer the reader to the document [1], which is freely available on Zenodo.

As of my recent writing [2]¹, I have been thinking about infinitesimal deformations introduced by quantum gravity. I considered a non-commutative bi-spectral form for the gravitational flux, $\bar{\mathcal{B}}\mathcal{F}$, which I will import here. The string-scale measure of this flux would be in units something like $10^{-70}J$, since the corresponding mass and distance scales are respectively $10^{-35}kg$ and $10^{-35}m$. This is enough work to accelerate a photon roughly to $c^2 \cdot \hbar$, which gives us a momentum of

$$P_{G_h} = \frac{h \cdot \int}{\ell \cdot \int} c^2 \hbar = hc\hbar = \frac{c \cdot h^2}{2\pi} kg \cdot m/s \tag{0.2}$$

which, in natural units:

$$= 1 \frac{kg \cdot m/s}{2\pi} = 1S \tag{0.3}$$

making it a unit of rotational momentum. I would like to refer to the unit S as the ‘‘Schwarzschild.’’

A References

[1] R.J. Buchanan, *Bordism Field Theories*, 2024

¹This is, of course, also available through Zenodo :)